

Customer Satisfaction towards Home Appliances Products in Tirupattur Talu

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Introduction

In a purchaser's market where the customer is the king, business begins and ends with the customer. The business development, gain fullness, liquidity and picture of an association rely on the customer. It is therefore fundamental that a provider meets the customer's desires completely and guarantees that he is satisfied. Thus it is important to put accentuation on building and keeping up consumer loyalty by putting the customer first in all exercises. Consumer satisfaction is the customer's perception that a vendor has met his desire completely, effectively and quickly.

A Home appliance is an electronic/mechanical machine which achieves some family unit capacities, for example, cooking or cleaning.

Purchasing is a dynamic process. Purchase of good is by far the most important function in society. The customer does devote a lot of time energy and attention to marketing a purchase decision. It is a well-known fact that there are many factors which that influence the customer home appliances such as efficiency of the product, the price of easy replacement of parts, guarantee period, the advertisement about the product, influence of friends, relatives, self-interest and family members

The customer marker consists of all home appliance and individuals who buy goods and service for their personal use. Customer differs tremendously in income, educational level and age. So it is necessary for the marker to divide customer. Within such decent varieties among customer, there are many likenesses among them. To discover these, the investigation of target customer needs perceptions and shopping and purchasing conduct will be useful as it will give the data important to growing new items, value, channels communication and other marketing components.

Consumer satisfaction is the investigation of existing business sector structure for the item, for example, Television, refrigerator,

washing machine and grinder. Effect of consumer satisfaction as a tool is confirming preference among the four products. A firm should build up a ceaseless stream of successful new products and services to stay young and productive. The strain to present effective new products is impressively increasing by the way that considerable item presentations and frequently because the organization has lacking data about what customer truly need. With the proliferation of specialized know-how, the market is floated with a few brands of a similar article. Each brand has minor varieties recognizing it from the others. Stiff competition obliges every product articles to endeavor to enhance the item and to give numerous extra offices and different attractions as could reasonably be expected. In the aggressive area, the customer attitudes of mind choose the existence of the specific business in the long run.

Objectives of the Study

- To know the awareness of customers towards home appliances products.
- To analysis the sources of information and motivating factors for the buy of home appliances.
- To think about the level of fulfillment towards home appliances products.
- To examine the satisfaction level of customer of contrast portion.
- To develop a consumer satisfaction show in light of the finding of the examination.

Statement of the Problem

The customer ponders inside herself before she at long last influences a buy to move. This pondering identifies with numerous factors and is gone for taking care of their utilization issues. Among these issues, the as a matter of first importance is to choose whether to burn through cash and the second issue is the thing that to purchase because the requirements are frightened. The Increase in double income families has led to the crunch of availability of time for shopping for home appliances items for the family. People are all looking for new ways of shopping of home with their limited available time and also, offer of electronic items was simple in the presentation arrange, however now all the home appliances venders faces cost of issue to offer its items because of the presence of contenders, who have been giving electronic products at bringing down costs.

Scope of the Study

The investigation goes for examining consumer satisfaction home appliances items. Television, Refrigerator, Washing machine, Grinder. The scope of the study has been limited to certain purchasing satisfaction parts of customer parts of the above-said durables, such as life style perception. The main motivation is its relationship between consumer behavior and product satisfaction. The researcher finds a very wide scope between products satisfaction that changes the mentality of the customer during the purchase of the durable product. The second motivation is to distinguish the satisfaction of the customer at the pre-buy and post-buy periods. They want customers to learn about their products; product attributes potential benefit. The analysis of customer preferences, perception and consumption of home appliances products.

Research Methodology

Area of the Study

Tirupattur is a town, located in Vellore District. Tirupattur is a part of Tamil Nadu state. The Headquarter Taluk is the town of Tirupattur. This emerging town is also known as “SANDALWOOD CITY” known for its rich and pure sandalwoods. Which is one of the oldest towns in Tamil Nadu. It is located Approximately 40 km Krishnagiri, 85 km from Hosur, 85 km from Thiruvannamalai and 125 km from Bangalore. The town has mainly small-scale industries and mills. It is well connected

by the road and rail to other important cities of Tamil Nadu such as Thiruvannamalai, Chennai, Salem, Coimbatore and Vellore and Bangalore in Karnataka. The name of Tirupattur means a group of ten villages connected with the small towns. As of 2011, the town had a population of 64,125. Tirupattur Municipality was constituted as a third-grade municipality in the year 1886. As per G.O. No.194, date 10.02.1970, classified as second Grade municipality. At present from 01.04.1977 onwards as per G.O.No.654, Tirupattur is classified as the first-grade municipality.

Demographics

According to 2011 census, the city of Tirupattur had a population of 63,798. Males constituted 51% of the population and females 49%. Tirupattur had an average literacy rate of 78%, significantly higher than the national average of 59.5%: male's literacy was 80% and female literacy was 76%. In 2011 in Tirupattur, 11% of the population was under total population 63.798 with the sex-ratio of 32,537 females for every 31,261 males, much above the national average of 929. A total of 7,255 were under the age of six, constituting 3,717 males and 3,538 females. Scheduled Castes and scheduled tribes accounted for 18.33% and 0.43% of the population respectively. Literacy of the town was 17.22%. The total of 14084 households. Workers. As per religious census of 2011, Tirupattur (M) had 71.93% Hindus, 26.39% Muslims, 1.52% Christians, 0.01% Sikhs 0.01% Buddhists, 0.47% Jains, 0.26% following other religious and 0.0% following no religion or did not indicate any religious preference.

Geography

It is known as the "sandalwood town" due to the abundant availability of sandalwood trees in the surrounding hills. It is very close the 4th major hill station of Tamil Nadu, the Yelagiri hills, which is also known as the common man's Ooty. The town is at an average elevation of 388 m.

Infrastructure

The Tirupattur town has 56.059 km length of roads and the municipality is maintaining 'B' Grade Bus stand in the heart of the town. There is a country old municipal market having 413 shops which help in promoting the commercial and economic activities of the town. Politics and municipal administration Tirupattur assembly constituency is a part of Thiruvannamalai (Lok Sabha constituency). Present MLA of Tirupattur assembly constituency is Mr.A.Nallathambi. Present MP of the Thiruvannamalai Lok Sabha Constituency is Mrs.R.Vanaroja.

Sample Size

The study covered a sample size of 120 respondents belong to the study area, who bought home appliances of electronic goods.

Data Collection

Primary Data

Primary data are those, which are collected fresh and for the first time, and thus it happens to be original. The study was mainly based on primary data.

Secondary Data

Secondary data means the data are already available they referred to the data which have already been collected and analyzed by someone else. Considerable data has also been from secondary sources such as Journals, Newspapers, Magazines and the Internet.

Research Design

Field Study

The field work of the study was carried out by the researcher. It was conducted during the period 2017-2018

Pilot Study

The topic was finalized as customer satisfaction towards home appliances products in Tirupattur. The researcher went to the field area to find the feasibility of the study. Customer view point to collect the questionnaire from respondents. The non Random sampling method was applied. The cronach alpha method t-square method is applied to check the reliability of the statements in the questionnaire. The tests revealed that the alpha value is 0.917 and t-square value is 245.17 which are statistically significant.

Pre Testing

As a result of pre-testing in a few modifications were modes according to the respondent's convenience. The research has asked 15 questionnaires and asked them to fill it the research had prepared the final questionnaire by eliminating repeated questions and by adding the questions based on the pretesting.

Table 1 Buy Home Appliances Product of the Respondents Factors

Buy Home Appliances product	Frequency	Percent
Retail seller	45	37.5
Whole seller	41	34.2
Through agent	8	6.7
Through online	26	21.7
Total	120	100.0

Limitations

This examination is restricted to geological base of Tirupattur covering a constrained population of the customer. The sample size has been restricted to 120 customers in various Tirupattur. The items chose for study are from purchaser durables viz. Television, Refrigerator, Washing machine, and Grinder. In choosing the brand and limitation is forced given the market availability.

Suggestions

1. Based on the finding of the study, the research would like to suggest the following:
2. The customer is suggested improving the durable customer products.
3. The customer is satisfied with the easy quality selected of the product.
4. It is suggested that the product should be newly made of the goods.
5. Customer goes by the quality while making the purchase. Hence, the supplier should maintain and Enhance the quality of the products.
6. The customer is suggested to avoid frequent use of self-interest while purchasing both home Appliances products.
7. People are unsatisfied with the price and quality of products.
8. According to the study, the awareness of the customer over the home appliances seems to be
9. Low. Hence step should be taken to increase the awareness level through various word of mouth.

Conclusion

Survey of the people has been conducted to know the liking pattern of the products. It is observed that overall people like to purchase quality. It is concluded that mostly people preferred due to its style. Therefore, the study of customer satisfaction is very vital to target the entire customer from different demographical areas. The research that has been carried out in Tirupattur town brings to light certain important facts. The customer is quality conscious and there is a need to make them more and more aware of home appliances. At the same time, customers are not so price conscious and they are ready to pay the price if they are convinced about the quality. Hence the research feels that the manufacture could keep this fact in mind so that the sales as well as the customer purchase satisfaction will be positive.

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